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RIDERS AN EMPLOYEE STATUS**

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Delivering Essentials Amid a Pandemic without Rights or Labor Protection: Proving the Use of Independent Contractor Agreements to Deny Food Panda Riders an Employee Status

Glades Jane B. Maglunsod*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Food delivery riders have gained widespread significance when countries went into lockdown to prevent the spread of COVID-19. Particularly in the Philippines, two major companies – Grab and Food Panda – employ thousands of delivery riders as “independent contractors,” sans any insurance or protection. This paper argues that food delivery riders, in line with the nature of their work, should be aptly recognized as employees of their digital platforms and should be accorded the proper benefits, protection, and compensation. Notwithstanding the cautious phrasing in the agreements signed by the delivery riders classifying them as independent contractors, it is the submission of this research that the law remains the primary factor that determines the relationship between the parties. As such, an employer-employee relationship, as laid down in Philippine jurisprudence, covers food delivery riders. The paper likewise cites landmark rulings from Spain and France, which recognized delivery riders and drivers as employees of their digital platforms. It is high time that such practices of food delivery businesses be corrected in favor of worker’s rights and a decent, gainful livelihood.

Keywords: *delivery riders, digital platforms, gig economy, independent contractors, labor protection*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the poor working conditions and the lack of labor protection for workers in the gig economy, particularly delivery riders whose work has been crucial amid the pandemic. They have been deemed essential workers for maintaining the flow of medicine, food, groceries, and household supplies in the economy.

Delivery riders are classified as belonging to the gig economy, which generally pertains to piece-work arrangements that are built on temporary and casual work. Food delivery drivers have gained widespread significance when countries went into lockdown to prevent the spread of COVID-19. Particularly in the Philippines, Food Panda is among the top companies which employ thousands of delivery riders as “independent contractors” sans any insurance or protection. The pandemic has brought along an opportune time to inquire into the practice of food delivery businesses of classifying their riders as independent contractors to place them outside the coverage of labor protection, and correct such practices in favor of workers’ rights and a decent, gainful livelihood. This research, thus, argues that applying the tests laid down in Philippine jurisprudence to determine the existence of an employer-employee relationship, Food Panda delivery riders are employees of their app-based company. As such, they should be aptly recognized as employees of their digital platforms and should be accorded the proper benefits, protection, and compensation.

Food Panda delivery riders in the Philippines are at the cusp of a legal and political battle for their recognition as employees, and not merely as “independent contractors.” Notwithstanding the cautious phrasing in the agreements signed by the delivery riders classifying them as independent contractors, it is the submission of this research that the law remains the primary factor that determines the relationship between the parties. This research will thus probe not only the legal foundation of classifying Food Panda delivery riders as employees, but likewise include the economic and social impacts of such a recognition. The issues raised and addressed by this research are currently real-life controversies that are pending in court. Moreover, an interrogation into the legal status of delivery riders, as contextualized by the country’s legal system, will have an extensive impact on delivery riders in general, as well as to other workers in the gig economy. This issue sets a precedent and explores a possibility for gig workers to be recognized as employees of their respective companies.

A ‘gig’ generally pertains to piece-work arrangements that are temporary and unpredictable, and a gig economy is a system built on such temporary and casual work. Woodcock and Graham (2020) describe the ‘gig economy’ as labor markets that are “characterized by independent contracting that happens through digital platforms,” where supply and demand are matched through algorithms. The term ‘gig economy’ is synonymous with ‘independent contracting,’ ‘sole proprietorship,’ or ‘freelancing,’ which tout flexibility at the expense of workers’ protection. Uber, Deliveroo, and Grab are examples of such digital platforms which hire workers under a self-employed or independent contractor status and consequently takes them away from the coverage of labor laws inconspicuously. Workers’ rights and social protection strike at the core of the gig economy, as the legal status of gig workers remains the elephant in the room. After all, staying in the “grey area” and insisting on the lack of an employment relationship free companies from the obligation to provide labor protection mandated by labor laws. No less than the International Labor Organization describes disguised employment in the gig economy as an underhanded arrangement that seeks to nullify the protection afforded to workers by law, as many jurisdictions continue to restrict these rights and protection only to those classified as employees (International Labor Organization, n.d.).

Digital platforms organize work through algorithms in smartphone apps, bridging both the worker and the customer. As these workers get paid on a per-task basis, delivery riders push the boundaries to finish as many deliveries as possible, even to the extent of going

over the speed limit, beating the red light, and working long hours, which increases their vulnerability to road collisions and accidents (Christie & Ward, 2019). The business model used by food delivery companies incentivizes continuous work, which drives workers to extreme fatigue. While the flexibility of their work arrangement gives them the control to self-regulate and stop working for several days, the high-pressure environment created by the gig economy precludes them from such options. Instead, it propels them towards risky behaviors, such as accepting continuous deliveries despite poor weather conditions, with little regard for their safety. Moreover, as with delivery riders, while the gig economy allows them to take various jobs simultaneously, many consider making deliveries as their full-time employment (Cherry & Rutschman, 2020).

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, delivery riders have gained recognition as “essential workers,” as their work allowed others to stay safely at home (Cherry & Rutschman, 2020). From essential food items to medicine, groceries, and other basic household supplies, countries turned to delivery riders to facilitate the flow of goods amid lockdowns and movement restrictions. As COVID-19 and corresponding government policies immobilized most of the population, this created more demand for delivery riders, but the situation is far from ideal. In effect, the work of delivery riders has become more precarious during the pandemic, as they have to additionally deal with health-related risks without protective gear.

Notwithstanding the increased precariousness of workers on the ground, digital platforms, on the other hand, have experienced a boom, with app-based delivery platforms all over the world experiencing exponential growth in 2020 (Altenreid et al., 2021; Campisi, 2020). However, this increase in profit did not translate to better working conditions, better protection, nor better pay for food delivery riders, as app-based companies did not sponsor vaccination programs for their riders, nor did they distribute free masks or other protective equipment. Despite being the main drivers of this growth for companies and the recognition that delivery riders perform essential work, there is much to be gained in ensuring labor protection and transparent wage structures for such workers. Delivery riders in the Philippines, for example, have protested not only the lack of insurance coverage and social protection but also untransparent wage structures, as the algorithms that determine their schedules, ratings, and corresponding pay are not understood by the riders themselves. While Cherry & Rutschman (2020) are correct in pointing out that the pandemic can create an opportunity that will lead to temporary rights and protections for delivery riders and other gig workers, this conversation should likewise be steered towards correcting the imbalances in the gig economy and introducing adjustments to tilt the scale in favor of labor rights and protection.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this research is to outline the jurisprudence and legal foundation that delivery riders are covered under the Philippine law’s definition of an employee, and thus should be accorded labor protection and other benefits under the Labor Code and other relevant laws. This research also seeks to probe the independent contracts signed by Food Panda delivery riders to further support the conclusion that notwithstanding their alleged status as “independent contractors,” that they are indeed employees as defined by the Philippine law. The main objective can be realized thru the following specific objectives:

- Provide jurisprudential context on what constitutes employer-employee relationship in the Philippine legal system;
- Examine the independent contracts of Food Panda workers and link it with current jurisprudence on what constitutes an employer-employee relationship; and
- Identify the legal and economic considerations made by the courts from other countries in landmark rulings that identify food delivery riders and other workers in the gig economy as employees, regardless of contracts which expressly state otherwise; and
- Develop recommendations as to how food delivery riders in the Philippines can access labor and social protection.

Literature Review

Recognizing Delivery Riders as Workers of their Digital Platforms: A Precedent in Spain, France, and the UK

There is no uniform manner in defining the elements of an employer-employee relationship across various countries, but there are striking similarities. In the European Union (EU), an employee is considered such if he does not control the time, place, content, and manner of accomplishing his work, and is thus incorporated into the economic unit which determines the worker’s conduct in the market (Vicente, 2019). Litigation on the rights of gig workers has centered upon their status – on whether they are to be considered traditional employees who fall under the coverage of labor laws or are independent contractors. EU countries such as Spain and France have initially signified that delivery riders should enjoy employment protections, as there is sufficient control and surveillance that business platforms have over such workers (Cherry & Rutschman, 2020; Vicente, 2019).

The general conceptualization of traditional employees and independent contractors is the same: the former pertains to necessary and desirable workers to the employer's business, while the latter refers to those with flexible schedules and enjoy minimal oversight from employers. Workers in the gig economy are characterized by both such features of traditional employees and independent contractors. While there are ongoing debates on the classification of delivery riders, there are significant precedents set forth by other countries which boldly decided that said workers are employees too. Currently, judicial intervention seems to be among the primary routes to effect a favorable outcome in favor of delivery riders and place them under the coverage of labor laws. However, as seen in the cited cases, this necessitates additional legislation to ensure that the misclassification of riders is addressed for the benefit of all.

The Case of Spain: Delivery Riders are Employees too

While there is an existing recognition of workers in the gig economy of Spain as self-employed workers whose rights and benefits are determined under the Self-employed Workers' Statute Act of 2017, a September 2020 decision of the Supreme Court ruled that riders from food delivery company Glovo are the latter's employees, and not economically dependent self-employed workers. Known as the "Riders Law," the Supreme Court of Spain held that Glovo, as a company that provides delivery and courier services, sets the price, payment conditions, and other essential conditions to carry out the said service, while its workers lack autonomy or control over the production process (Industrial Relations and Labour Law, 2020; Perez, 2021). In its rationale, as translated by the Industrial Relations and Labour Law (2020), the Supreme Court of Spain ruled in this wise:

[Glovo] is a company that provides delivery and courier services, setting the price and payment conditions for the service, as well as the essential conditions for the provision of said service. And it is the owner of the essential assets to carry out the activity. To do this, it uses distributors who do not have their own and autonomous business organization, who provide their services within the employer's organization of work, subject to the management and organization of the platform, as evidenced by the fact that Glovo establishes all aspects related to the form and price of the collection and delivery service of said products. That is, both the form of provision of the service, as well as its price and form of payment are established by Glovo. The company has established instructions that allow it to control the production process. [...]. The rider neither organizes the productive activity by himself, nor negotiates prices or conditions with the owners of the establishments he/she serves, nor does he receive his/her remuneration from the end customers. The claimant did not have a true capacity to organize his work provision, lacking autonomy to do so. It was subject to the organizational guidelines set by the company. (Emphasis supplied)

The Supreme Court of Spain also found out that riders under Glovo can be sanctioned on the basis of guidelines set forth by the company. While there is no physical supervision of Glovo over the riders, the digital platform allows the latter real-time control and can monitor the time, distance, number of deliveries, amount paid, and assessment from customers. The algorithms that allow assessment of each rider impact their "theoretical freedom to choose timetables and to reject orders." Thus, while there is a level of flexibility that characterizes the relationship between the digital platform and its riders, the basic element of control is markedly present in the manner that Glovo's organization of its service. The immediate implication of this Supreme Court ruling, according to Spain's Labour Minister, is that delivery riders who are now considered employees of their digital platforms will be classified as salaried workers, and enjoy all the relevant labor protections, thereby effectively transforming the contractual relationship between the parties (France 24, 2020; Industrial Relations and Labour Law, 2020). This is despite adamant resistance from digital platforms, which continue to insist that they are mere intermediaries between customers and riders, and thus should not be made to pay the health and pension contributions of their riders.

There is a continuing dialogue between the riders, riders' associations, lawmakers, digital platforms, trade unions, Spain's labor department, among other stakeholders, to thresh out how this new Riders Law will be implemented. This is particularly important since app-based companies are raising issues of possible closures due to said new regulations. While there are various perspectives from both riders and their digital platform employers, it is undeniable that this landmark legislation – deemed as the first in the European Union – is long-overdue recognition for workers in the gig economy, and an important precedent for the rest of the world.

The Case of France: A relationship of subordination is established between the driver and the company

Though particularly in relation to Uber and with regard to drivers, as opposed to delivery riders, a short discussion on France's Supreme Court decision is likewise merited as it involved a similar relationship between app-based companies and their workers. In 2020, the Cour de Cassation, the top court in France, affirmed a ruling that an Uber driver of the taxi-hailing app Uber is an employee of the latter and not a self-employed contractor. The Cour de Cassation held that a relationship of subordination is created once the driver logs on to the app, where he loses control of setting the prices or building his own clientele, thus making him a subordinate of Uber (Rosemain & Vidalon, 2020). The said court goes further to state that when an Uber driver provides services to a customer, he does so as an employee of Uber. The decision is primarily based on the legal ground set forth in a 1996 decision, which provided for the essential characteristics of an employer-employee relationship, to wit:

"A relationship of subordination is characterized by the performance of work under the authority of an employer which has the power to give orders and directives, to control the performance of work and to sanction the lack of performance of its subordinate." While the decision has been met with resistance from Uber as it could lead to more drivers seeking reclassification and acknowledgment as Uber's employees, the Labor Chamber of the Cour de Cassation states that said ruling will not lead to automatic classification of drivers in the gig economy. Nonetheless, this is a step in the right direction for workers in the gig economy with no health insurance and other benefits.

The Case of the United Kingdom: Creating a New Classification for Workers in the Gig Economy

In a July 2020 decision, Britain's Supreme Court ruled that Uber drivers are workers of the digital app-based platform Uber. This recent ruling implies that drivers, which were previously classified as self-employed or independent contractors, are now entitled to minimum pay, health benefits, and other workers' rights (Adam, 2021). The Court created a separate classification – that of "workers" – which is different from employees or independent contractors, and something of a middle ground. This unusual category gives additional

rights to Uber drivers, such as paid holidays, pension contributions, and minimum wage, but they are short of enjoying the full benefits of employees, as they are not entitled to sick pay, parental leave and have fewer protections against unjust dismissal (Mishel & McNicholas, 2021).

Particularly, Britain's Supreme Court ruled that Uber drivers are to be considered the company's workers from the time that they log on to the app and until such time that they log off. Effectively creating a new classification, the Supreme Court highlighted several factors which strengthen the contention that drivers are "workers" of Uber. This includes the fact that Uber interviews and recruits its drivers; that Uber controls the key information and excludes the driver from it; that Uber requires drivers to accept trips and not to cancel, lest they be sanctioned; that Uber sets the default route and a driver will be sanctioned if it does not follow such; that Uber fixes the fare; that Uber imposes numerous restrictions such as the choice of acceptable vehicles and other guidelines in the performance of their work; that Uber subjects their drivers to a rating system that determines performance management and disciplinary procedures; that Uber controls issues on rebates without informing its drivers; that Uber accepts the risk of loss which would not be the case if Uber drivers were indeed self-employed; that Uber handles complaints of passengers; and that Uber reserves the power to make and amend the drivers' contract unilaterally. This decision to create a new classification is an alternative that creates a middle ground for all the parties involved – better rights and protection but not full rights as enjoyed by an employee and greater responsibility but not full responsibility as those imposed to an employer.

The COVID-19 pandemic and the urgency for workers' protection

The pandemic has put a spotlight on the poor working conditions of workers in the gig economy. With global restrictions, delivery riders and others in the gig economy have taken the role of ensuring the flow of goods despite the restriction on people's mobility. Yet, they have no added protection, no health insurance if they contract COVID-19, and no benefits or insurance when they get sick or meet accidents on the road. The pandemic has further escalated the demand in the "on-demand" gig economy, which has left gig workers exhausted but with no option for paid leave, sick leave, and other social protection. The rule is simple – they do not get paid if they do not work, pushing many to the brink of fatigue. Thus, as the digital platforms have raked in the profits amid the pandemic (Sumagaysay, 2020; Dishman, 2020; Campisi, 2020), there was no stark improvement in the condition of their workers on the ground; there is no free provision of masks or alcohol, no scheduling for vaccinations, not even health checks. In South Korea, Japan, and the Philippines, there has been a continuous protest over the legal status of delivery riders. Despite the challenge of fragmentation in workers in the gig economy, as they are not in one place and do not fall within the traditional definitions of "strikes" or "industry-wide actions" (Vicente, 2019), delivery riders have responded to their situation with various forms of protests, and even litigation.

In 2019, UberEats delivery staff in Japan formed their labor union, bringing together an estimated 15,000 delivery riders in Japan to demand safer working conditions and better protections for delivery riders (Kyodo News, 2019). Delivery riders have referred to themselves as "platform workers" and are demanding transparency and proper computation in what is called distance-based wages. While there is no ruling in Japanese courts regarding the classification of delivery riders as employees, the collective action of delivery riders and their demands have led to the Japanese Labor Ministry's approval of the proposal to allow said riders to join workers' accident compensation programs under a special coverage system, giving them protection in cases of accidents, disability, or death (Arab News, 2021). The said compensation program previously only covered employees but has now accommodated delivery riders who are set to receive proper compensation and subsidized medical costs when they are involved in accidents. In South Korea, increased shipping demands due to the pandemic have led to protests by drivers and delivery riders, with reports that 14 drivers have already suffered heart attacks or strokes as a direct result of overwork (Bicker, 2020). Delivery riders and their families have tapped South Korea's National Assembly and sought to get the attention of the country's President, to call for an overhaul of working conditions for delivery employees, including delivery riders who continuously work overnight shifts but are outside the protection and benefits provided by labor laws (Bicker, 2020).

The same situation was glaringly familiar in the Philippine set-up, this time involving delivery riders of app-based delivery company Food Panda. Food Panda riders had protested and complained of the lack of social protection, health benefits, and even transparency in their wage structure, despite them working double due to the demands created by the pandemic (Francisco, 2021; Llemit, 2021; Paje, 2021). Instead of compromise, the delivery riders were met with a 10-year suspension. Despite recent developments, the delivery riders were able to form their own association while a few of its members have filed complaints against the Food Panda management before the National Labor Relations Commission, the administrative body tasked with settling labor disputes in the country (Cortez, 2021). The string of cases and protests led by delivery riders is an indication of the urgent need to address the issue of the classification of food delivery riders, or at the very least, the introduction of mechanisms to improve their current working conditions. Delivery riders are defying traditional definitions and are able to organize despite the fragmentation caused by the individualized nature of their work. The same campaign and push for legal recognition of delivery riders have been successful in Spain, France, and the United Kingdom, where limited victories have been achieved legally in recognizing delivery riders as workers or employees of their digital platforms.

Methodology

Research Design

This study is a qualitative case study on the legal status of delivery riders, and whether Philippine law and jurisprudence can cover said

delivery riders under the definition of “employees.”

The research is a case study on Food Panda delivery drivers and their particular independent contractor contracts. Merriam (2002) defines a case study as an intensive description and analysis of a social unit, such as a specific group or community. Case studies do not establish causation between variables through comparison, but it does provide evidence in a single case that is testable and can also be weighed against similar case studies dealing with the same subject matter (Bennett & Elman, 2006). This case study focuses on Food Panda delivery riders in Davao City, their existing contracts and campaigns, in relation to current jurisprudence and law on employer-employee relationship.

Participants

The research data will include key informant interviews with Food Panda delivery riders in Davao City. Lawyers and labor experts will likewise be included in the KII. The researcher will also gather information from random Food Panda delivery riders through a questionnaire. Moreover, the research will conduct desk review and documentary evidence to establish the baseline data and current jurisprudence on the status of delivery riders, or casual employees, in relation to relevant Supreme Court rulings, Department of Labor and Employment Circulars, among other pertinent resources. Likewise, the desk review and documentary evidence will include an in-depth analysis of the contracts between Food Panda management and its delivery riders. The data is triangulated by the interview results, the questionnaire, and the desk review’s outcome.

The study utilized purposive sampling to determine the respondents of this study. Purposive sampling involves selecting participants who can provide detailed an in-depth data or information about a particular subject of the study (Etikan, 2016; Luborsky & Rubinstein, 1995). Etikan (2016) describes it as a non-random technique wherein the researcher decides what needs to be known and finds people who can provide information by virtue of their knowledge and experience. Purposive sampling involves the identification of individuals who are proficient and knowledgeable on the topic. Particularly for this study, a homogenous purposive sampling was conducted wherein participants were selected on the basis of their being Food Panda delivery riders, members of the Food Panda management, or lawyers and labor experts.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher summarized the descriptive data from the questionnaire and interview into keywords and grouped them thematically to generate a prevailing assessment of Food Panda delivery riders vis-à-vis those that are members of the management. The insights in one parameter are compared with each other. Other data from the desk review and other documentary evidence gathered will likewise be utilized to expound on the results and ground the findings to the jurisprudence context

In the analysis of the descriptive data from the questionnaires, key informant interviews, and desk review, the research makes use of the thematic content analysis, wherein themes and categories which emerge from the data are identified and grouped into a dataset. Since the analysis focuses on providing an in-depth description of individuals' knowledge and assessment, the data gathered will aid in identifying patterns and salient themes that depict variations in how social phenomena are articulated and experienced by the respondents. The transcription of the descriptive data gathered, which includes appropriate labeling and the thematic content analysis, will enable the researcher to explore general themes and patterns on the plight and demands of Food Panda delivery riders in comparison to the rationalization and response of the management. This will also be correlated to the results of the desk review, i.e., the in-depth examination of the contracts and the prevailing legal and jurisprudential backdrop to enable the research to arrive at a plausible conclusion as to whether delivery riders can be considered employees of their digital platforms.

Results and Discussion

This section will discuss the findings of the researcher, sourced from desk review, questionnaires, and the KII with labor experts and lawyers. It will also cover application of jurisprudence to the particular context of Food Panda delivery riders vis-à-vis their company, Food Panda.

Collectively Asserting the Legal Status of Food Panda Delivery Riders as Employees

A questionnaire among the Food Panda delivery riders yielded the following as their primary concerns:

In July 2021, Food Panda riders in Davao City held a protest to complain of the reduced earnings and change in their wage structure, which was not made clear to them (Francisco, 2021). Prior to the July 2021 protest, delivery riders of the same company in the country's capital, Manila, also held a protest in front of the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) in November 2020 over unfair labor practices and to likewise protest the new payment scheme of Food Panda (Santos, 2020). The riders in Luzon and Mindanao, where Food Panda's operations have been widespread, similarly claim that despite the increase in demand and work due to the pandemic, they have been receiving less in their payments due to the unfair grading system newly imposed by the company (Santos, 2020; Cortez, 2021). The riders have since formed an association and have likewise started to question their status as employees of the app-based company. The questionnaire and the interviews conducted by the researcher reveal that while the Food Panda delivery riders initially questioned the imposition of business permits and other fees against them individually, this common issue allowed them to organize and collectively push for their assertion to be recognized as employees of Food Panda, instead of mere independent contractors.

From the above list of concerns, the Food Panda delivery riders formed their own association, namely the Davao United Delivery Riders Association Inc. (DUDRAI) in 2021. It is through the formation of this organization that the Food Panda delivery riders started to assert their legal status as employees of Food Panda, contending that there exists an employer-employee relationship between them and the company. Through the officers of DUDRAI, a case for illegal dismissal was filed by a number of delivery riders against Food Panda. The main issue is whether there is an employer-employee relationship between the parties. If there is, then Food Panda is liable for illegal dismissal, and should pay the riders their respective money claims. If, however, the riders are mere independent contractors, then Food Panda is not liable to the former. This case is currently ongoing and will be thoroughly discussed in subsequent sections. Regardless, the outcome of this case has wide repercussions for all delivery riders in the gig economy. If the courts decide that they are indeed employees of their app-based companies, then it would entitle delivery riders to labor standard laws, which includes overtime pay, 13th month pay, holiday pay, premium pay, maternity leave, paternity leave, service incentive leave, among others.

Right to Control Test

In the Philippine jurisdiction, there is a test used by the Labor Department and by the courts to determine whether a person is classified as an independent contractor or an employee – the right to control test. Under this test, an employer-employee relationship is deemed to exist if the person or company for whom the services are performed "reserves the right to control not only the end to be achieved but also the manner and means to be used in reaching the end." Subsequent jurisprudence has further refined the determination of this relationship, with the Philippine Supreme Court ruling that it is not necessary for a person to be under the supervision of physical workplace of the employer to be deemed an employee, so long as the element of control is present in the manner that the person does her work. Moreover, the Court further made a qualification in a later case that continuity, or even exclusivity, of employment is not the determining factor on whether a person is an employee, but it is whether the work is "part of the regular business or occupation of the employer." Other tests alongside the right to control that can also be weighed in to determine an employer-employee relationship are the selection and engagement of the employee, payment of wages, and power of dismissal (Ungos & Ungos, 2020). Collectively, these are deemed as the "four-fold test", but it is the control test which is most crucial.

The country's Labor Department has already said it will issue a guideline on whether riders of food delivery apps can be considered employees (Medenilla, 2021). Notwithstanding this, this paper argues that the relationship between Food Panda and its delivery riders ticks off all the checklists in the right of control test, and thus there is sufficient legal basis for arguing that delivery riders should be considered employees of their digital platforms.

Probing Food Panda's Service Provider Agreement

Akin the defense forwarded by other digital platforms, their first line of argument of said companies would be to reference the contract that was signed between the parties. This can be considered self-serving on the part of Food Panda since they are the party who drafted the contract, and it is unsurprising that they would state – in no uncertain terms – that the delivery riders are mere independent contractors or self-employed persons. In Food Panda's service agreement, admission to the following is required before an application is approved:

I agree that should the Company accept me as a Service Provider, I will throughout hold and continue to hold the status of a self-employed person and that the arrangement between me and the Company shall not, in any event or circumstances, constitute or be construed as a relationship of employer and employee, of principal and agent, of joint ventures or of partners, or of any other relationship of whatsoever nature, save and except that of independent contractor. I further acknowledge that I will not be entitled to any benefits offered or to be offered by the Company to its employees (whether permanent or temporary), including without limitation, the benefits of any pension scheme, any employer's liability insurance, medical insurance, life insurance, bonus or commission. (Emphasis added)

Food Panda has sufficiently and expressly enumerated that it is under no obligation to provide any benefits or protection to its riders and that the latter is self-employed. The contract even states that in no event or circumstances will the riders be considered as an employee of the company. Despite this safeguard put up by companies, however, the Philippine Supreme Court has reiterated in a catena of cases that an employer-employee relationship is determined by law and that "it cannot be negated by expressly repudiating it in a management contract and providing therein that the employee is an independent contractor when the terms of the agreement clearly show otherwise." The employment status of a person is defined not by the parties, but by the law.

In the same service agreement, Food Panda narrates the obligations of the delivery riders, which demonstrate direct control over the manner and means in which to perform the work. The following are the salient points that markedly show the company's direct control over the means, method, and outcome of the work:

First, Food Panda provides a series of shifts that riders can choose from, and the latter has to inform the former at least 24 hours before the start of the shift. Riders cannot just spontaneously log on to the app and take orders.

The rider is to use either an iPhone or Android smartphone that has to fit the company's requirements laid down in the agreement. Riders have to ensure the device could access voice and data services, and they could download the application on the approved device only. The software or application tracks order status, including pickup and delivery time, location, among others.

While the rider supplies his own vehicle, this has to fit the specifications provided by Food Panda. The service cannot commence if Food Panda determines the equipment or vehicle does not fit its criteria, and Food Panda retains the right to inspect the equipment from time to time at its discretion.

The company also provides specifications for the thermal bag, pizza bag, and bike box to be used by the rider and the latter has to be in a particular clothing designated by the company. Food Panda specifically gives instructions on the food delivery, from the time it is picked up from the restaurant to when it is delivered to the customer:

The rider is to pick up the package and put it in the isothermal bag, and it shall remain sealed from pick up to the final delivery.

Rider to put the isothermal bag in the designated enclosure in the vehicle and securely lock the enclosure; the rider is to ensure the temperature and presentation is maintained;

Rider to drive to customer's address and deliver the food as fast as possible while keeping the food in the best condition.

Rider shall open the isothermal bag in the presence of the customer and no time before that.

In cases where the order had not been previously paid, the rider is to take the amount and transfer it, in full and without reduction, on a weekly basis, to the company's accounting department.

Only the company handles complaints from the customers.

Food Panda reserves the right and has sole discretion to change the service fees at any time and shall notify the client of such change. It may also make deductions from the service fees if there is a non-return of delivery bags or non-remittance of cash collected from the client.

Riders are subjected to deductions if they don't accept two or more consecutive fulfillments during a shift selected by them. Deductions will also be imposed if there are delays in the delivery.

Lastly, Food Panda may add or modify the standards stated in the agreement at any time and at its sole discretion.

These are among the pertinent provisions in the service agreement that can be used as a basis to argue the existence of an employer-employee relationship between Food Panda and its delivery riders. The enumeration shows the extensive control of Food Panda on the conduct and performance of the work of its riders – from the specifications on the phone, the vehicle, up to the interactions with customers, the deductions, and even the scheduling. Similar to the situation of the delivery riders in Spain and the Uber drivers in Britain, Food Panda delivery riders do not organize the productive activity themselves, and they do not have a true capacity to organize their work provision, as they lacked the autonomy to do so and are under the organizational guidelines by the company. To simply dismiss their claim as employees simply because of the alleged flexibility would be superficial and erroneous, as the actual working relationship easily shows otherwise.

It is also important to mention that the same service agreement penalizes riders for bringing any employment-related claim based on their worker status, and the riders will even be obliged to indemnify the company arising from any employment-related claim:

The Contractor agrees not to bring any employment related claim or any claim based on worker status against the Company or any of its clients, arising out of or in connection with the provision of the Services. The Contractor shall indemnify the Company and any of its clients against any and all liability arising from any employment-related claim or any claim based on worker status x x x.

Indeed, the meticulousness of Food Panda in ensuring that the lack of an employer-employee relationship is expressly provided in the contract and in adding provisions that discourage riders from challenging their status betrays a recognition that they could be held liable as employers. As of this writing, suspended Food Panda riders have already filed a complaint before the National Labor Relations Commission, which will set the ball rolling in the resolution of the issue of their classification and legal status. It is important to emphasize that while the contract categorizes the riders as "independent contractors", this is not automatically controlling, as the law and the factual circumstances will ultimately be the last arbiter in determining whether an employer-employee relationship exists between the parties.

While there is a grey area, and others can argue that the interpretation could sway both ways, Article 1702 of the Civil may provide an

enlightening resolution. The said article provides that if there is doubt, “all labor contracts shall be construed in favor of the safety and decent living for the laborer.” Public policy provides that in cases of doubt, the interpretation should be in favor of riders being employees.

Labor Arbiter, NLRC declare the delivery riders as employees of Food Panda

In a decision issued on December 7, 2022, the National Labor and Relations Commission (NLRC) 8th Division affirmed the ruling of the Labor Arbiter (LA) that the delivery riders who filed a complaint of illegal dismissal against Food Panda Philippines, Inc. are the latter’s regular employees, and that said riders were indeed illegally dismissed from employment. The said NLRC decision held that there was an employer-employee relationship between Food Panda and the delivery riders because “the power of control was clearly wielded by [Food Panda] through extensive supervision from start of their assigned duty until it ends, the company’s actual prohibition of alternative employment, and its algorithmic disciplinary measures indicate strict supervision and control over its delivery riders.” Further, the NLRC also ruled that Food Panda’s act of suspending complainants for a period of 10 years is tantamount to constructive dismissal, thus the riders were illegally dismissed. This is in relation to Food Panda’s acts of denying complainants access to the Food Panda’s Rider Application for 10 years, following a demand by said riders for transparency regarding the calculation of their pay and corresponding deductions.

Food Panda denied the existence of an employer-employee relationship, and argued that the said riders were engaged as independent contractors. Food Panda relies on the contract, but the determination of an employer-employee relationship is not automatically based on the contract; it is based on the presence of control and the factual circumstances of the case. As argued in this research, since control is shown to be exercised by Food Panda in its relationship with its riders, then the latter is deemed an employee of the former. The NLRC not only considered the legal aspect of the case, but likewise its social and economic impacts to the lives and livelihood of the delivery riders. In dismissing the appeal of Food Panda, the NLRC concludes:

“In the still raging war against COVID-19, We take judicial notice of the fact that food delivery riders have repeatedly been alluded to as frontliners and heroes for enabling us to abide by physical distancing and other health protocols, while, at the same time, bolstering the economy. Nevertheless, while they have been hailed as heroes, they have not always been treated as such. As heroes, they should, at the very least, be able to demand minimum labor standard benefits, e.g. minimum wage, service incentive leave, right to organize and collective bargaining, and security of tenure provided under Philippine laws.” (Emphasis added)

While Food Panda will still appeal the decision to the Court of Appeals and subsequently, upon another adverse decision, to the Supreme Court, the favorable rulings of the administrative tribunals show that there is indeed strong basis in the assertion that the delivery riders are employees of Food Panda, and not merely independent contractors. Despite what may have been expressly written in the contract, it is still the actual relationship of the parties that will determine whether an employer-employee relationship exists. If these initial rulings are an indication of how this case will turn out, then it will be a long-awaited and landmark victory for delivery riders.

The victory of Food Panda delivery riders is crucial in setting a precedent. However, the decision may only be applicable to Food Panda riders, and does not automatically cover all delivery riders hired by other companies, such as Grab. It is this gap that a legislative measure, or a law, can fill. A law defining the relationship between app-based companies and delivery riders would enable a uniform recognition of the latter as employees. Such a legislative measure is among the recommendations put forward by this research.

Conclusions

This research looks into the struggle between the status of delivery riders for legal recognition as employees on the one hand, and the push back against this on the part of the management. More importantly, this backdrop is given jurisprudence context given the country’s laws and relevant Supreme Court rulings. While the tension between the riders and the management may be political, the ultimate arbiter in deciding whether riders can be considered employees is ultimately a legal question. Thus, this is the core at which the research seeks to provide a plausible resolution.

As mentioned, this research centers on the plight of Food Panda delivery riders in the Philippines and their continuing fight for recognition as employees. This research sought to provide a legal and political insight into the legal status of workers in the gig economy, particularly for food delivery riders who are classified as independent contractors and stripped off any labor protection. The current legal battle involving Food Panda and its delivery riders, as well as the initial decision of the labor tribunals, show that there is an urgency and a strong legal basis for taking this step forward for the recognition of the rights of delivery riders, and ultimately providing protection for said workers and their families. To this end, this research recommends legally challenging the contracts of the delivery riders wherein they are classified merely as “independent contractors”. This course of action is akin to the route undertaken by Food Panda riders, whose case is now favorable decided upon by the NLRC. However, for a long-term and more encompassing impact, the delivery riders and other advocates can call for the passage of a law which uniformly and clearly defines delivery riders as employees of their app-based companies. This is a challenging and long endeavor, but if successful, it can institutionalize delivery riders’ access and entitlement to labor standards and protection.

Moreover, the literature also shows that the situation of gig workers globally is uniform and that their manner of exploitation is likewise

similar. The use of contracts that expressly designate their status as independent contractors, sole proprietors, or self-employed are among the mechanisms that digital platforms use to shield themselves from any accountability and responsibility to provide protection, insurance, and workers' rights to delivery riders. However, not only did the cited jurisprudence decide against these express contractual stipulations designating delivery riders as independent contractors, but the respective high courts in Spain, UK, and France effectively ruled that such is secondary to the actual relationship between the parties – which is characterized by the element of control in the objective and the means of doing the work. The similarities in the rulings boil down to the element of control, which can be raised or cited as an analogous circumstance in other countries where there is pending litigation on the status of delivery riders. This result is the most favorable, as it operates to provide delivery riders full employment benefits, rights, and protections. Since there are similarities in cases decided in foreign jurisdictions, this implies that the actions and arguments undertaken by delivery riders in other countries may also be replicated here.

In sum, the conditions to challenge the status of gig workers and to call for greater protection are ripe. While there is a challenge unique to gig workers because they are fragmented and are not situated in one place, recent developments have shown that collective action and solidarity are very much alive among workers in the gig economy. There is much to be gained in challenging the legal status of riders in the courts and creating a legislative agenda, but equally important is the unity and solidarity among the delivery riders themselves. In the Philippines, delivery riders have formed associations to increase their bargaining power against app-based companies while simultaneously building camaraderie with their fellow riders. This is particularly salient during accidents and even deaths of fellow riders, where the lack of insurance is mitigated by small donations offered by each rider to the family of the deceased.

This conversation on the rights of workers in the gig economy is long overdue, and it took a pandemic to bring this issue to the fore. While judicial intervention and tapping the legislature are viable means to effect change for delivery riders, there is also value in building a movement centered around the recognition of riders as workers, as this creates pressure on the ground and can force the public to take notice. Recognizably, the power relations tilt more in favor of app-based companies, but lessons from the past are replete with successes in collective action. There is now an opportunity to take a step forward for the recognition of the rights of delivery riders, and it is a step that could resonate with others to likewise follow the trail. Thus, this research not only recommends a judicial and legislative route, but likewise the furthering of collective action among the delivery riders themselves.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Glades Jane B. Maglunsod

Philippine Christian University – Philippines